

Selection Process: Collaborative Lesson Development Training (CLDT) Call

Building digital skills training and lesson development capacity in the Netherlands NES domain (DC4NES) Project | 2026

Overview

The DC4NES project funds 3 teams of 2-3 people to join the Carpentries Collaborative Lesson Development Training (CLDT). This is a single open call. This document describes the application and selection process.

Timeline

- Call opens: 1 May – 31 July 2026
- Review and selection of applications: August 2026
- Training: November 2026, on location in the Netherlands (16 hours)
- Matchmaking session: 18 June, Utrecht (organized by RST-NL)

Process

1. The eligibility and selection criteria were informed by a survey distributed to the research community October 2025 – February 2026. Survey results are published on Zenodo and on the 4TU.ResearchData project page.
2. The project team (Carpentries Coordinators Network NL) develops the eligibility and selection criteria for the CLDT based on the survey results.
3. The call is announced via related DC4NES communication channels and networks: [4TU.ResearchData](#), [RST-NL](#), [TDCC-NES](#), [Carpentries NL TopicBox and Slack](#), DCC-PO mailing list, Coding Cafes, [Taxila.nl](#) and additional social media channels (e.g. LinkedIn).
4. Teams of 2–3 people submit an application via the application form. The application must include: a description of the proposed lesson, its target audience, its relevance to the NES domain, and confirmation of eligibility (including a description of institutional support). Eligibility and selection criteria are outlined in the Eligibility Criteria: CLDT Call and Selection Criteria: CLDT Call documents.
5. The project team checks all nominations against the eligibility criteria.
6. Nominations that do not meet the eligibility criteria are returned to the institution with a brief explanation. Institutions may resubmit before the deadline.
7. If 3 or fewer eligible applications are received, all are accepted.
8. If more than 3 eligible applications are received, the selection criteria are applied by the selection committee (Carpentries Coordinators Network NL). For selection criteria, see DC4NES_08_Selection_Criteria_CLDT document.
9. Accepted candidates are notified and receive practical information about the training.
10. Teams whose applications were not selected are informed with a brief explanation in August 2026.

Fallback provisions

If fewer than 3 eligible applications are received, the project team will either organize a second recruitment effort or reallocate unused funds for a third training opportunity, additional Instructor Training seats or workshop funding, as agreed by the consortium.

Decision-making

The project consortium acts as the selection committee when the call is oversubscribed. The WP2 lead coordinates the process and communicates decisions to all applicants.

Related documents

You can find all related documents in the Digital Capacity for NES community on Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/communities/dc4nes>

- Selection Criteria: CLDT Call
- Selection Process: CLDT Call